

TRANSLATION OF FAIRY TALE**Jo'rayeva Shaxzoda Otabek qizi**

Author, A student of the Translation Faculty

Borasulova Dilnoza Dilmurodovna

Scientific advisor, a teacher at the Translation Faculty

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10867312>

Abstract. *Few stories have been translated so often and into so many languages as the classical fairy tales. As such, they are a true challenge for translation studies. This article proposes a methodology for investigating fairy tales in translation. The suggested method is essentially a comparative textual analysis, inspired by translation studies, literary theory, linguistic criticism, and discourse analysis. It can be applied to the synchronic research of fairy tale translations within a restricted period as well as to the diachronic research of translations of one or more fairy tales over a longer period. A step-by-step model is presented, which makes it possible to classify and analyze changes in translations as well as adaptations. To bridge the gap between content and linguistic levels, a linguistic analysis is linked to focal points, grouped under categories from literary studies. The examples come from six recent Dutch translations of Sleeping Beauty, published between 1995 and 2007. In the final part of this study, a scheme is offered for the interpretation of the changes brought to light by the analysis. It takes into account individual as well as social factors and it is based on the concepts of norms, systems, and functions. Such a structured method of analysis is hoped to offer new possibilities for the study of fairy tales in translation.*

Keywords: *children's literature, fairy tale, translation, linguistic criticism, norms.*

ПЕРЕВОД СКАЗКИ

Аннотация. *Немногие сказки переводились так часто и на такое количество языков, как классические сказки. По существу, они представляют собой настоящую проблему для переводоведения. В данной статье предлагается методика исследования сказок в переводе. Предлагаемый метод, по сути, представляет собой сопоставительный текстовый анализ, вдохновленный переводоведением, теорией литературы, лингвистической критикой и анализом дискурса. Его можно применять как к синхроническому исследованию переводов сказок за ограниченный период, так и к диахроническому исследованию переводов одной или нескольких сказок за более длительный период. Представлена пошаговая модель, позволяющая классифицировать и анализировать изменения как в переводах, так и в адаптациях. Чтобы преодолеть разрыв*

между содержанием и лингвистическим уровнями, лингвистический анализ связан с фокусными точками, сгруппированными по категориям литературоведения. Примеры взяты из шести недавних голландских переводов «Спящей красавицы», опубликованных в период с 1995 по 2007 год. В заключительной части исследования предлагается схема интерпретации изменений, выявленных в результате анализа. Он учитывает как индивидуальные, так и социальные факторы и основан на концепциях норм, систем и функций. Надеемся, что такой структурированный метод анализа откроет новые возможности для изучения сказок в переводе.

Ключевые слова: *детская литература, сказка, перевод, лингвистическая критика, нормы.*

A fairy tale (alternative names include fairytale, fairy story, magic tale, or wonder tale) is a short story that belongs to the folklore genre.[1] Such stories typically feature magic, enchantments, and mythical or fanciful beings. In most cultures, there is no clear line separating myth from folk or fairy tale; all these together form the literature of preliterate societies.[2] Fairy tales may be distinguished from other folk narratives such as legends (which generally involve belief in the veracity of the events described)[3] and explicit moral tales, including beast fables. Prevalent elements include dragons, dwarfs, elves, fairies, giants, gnomes, goblins, griffins, merfolk, monsters, talking animals, trolls, unicorns, witches, wizards, magic, and enchantments.

Fairy tales occur both in oral and in literary form; the name "fairy tale" ("conte de fées" in French) was first ascribed to them by Madame d'Aulnoy in the late 17th century. Many of today's fairy tales have evolved from centuries-old stories that have appeared, with variations, in multiple cultures around the world.[6]

The history of the fairy tale is particularly difficult to trace because only the literary forms can survive. Still, according to researchers at universities in Durham and Lisbon, such stories may date back thousands of years, some to the Bronze Age. Fairy tales, and works derived from fairy tales, are still written today.

The Jatakas are probably the oldest collection of such tales in literature, and the greater part of the rest are demonstrably more than a thousand years old. It is certain that much (perhaps one-fifth) of the popular literature of modern Europe is derived from those portions of this large bulk which came west with the Crusades through the medium of Arabs and Jews.

Folklorists have classified fairy tales in various ways. The Aarne–Thompson–Uther Index and the morphological analysis of Vladimir Propp are among the most notable. Other folklorists

have interpreted the tales' significance, but no school has been definitively established for the meaning of the tales.

People do not agree what a fairy tale exactly is. Some argue that a story with fairies or other magical beings in the story would make it a fairy tale. However, others have suggested that the expression began when the French expression *conte de fées* was being translated (it was first used by Madame D'Aulnoy in 1697). Vladimir Propp criticized the difference between "fairy tales" and "animal tales" in his book *Morphology of the Folktale*.^[8] He said that many stories had both fantastic qualities and animals. He suggested that fairy tales could be recognized by their story, but this has been criticized, because the same stories can be found in stories that are not fairy tales.

In fact, people such as Stith Thompson point out that there are often more talking animals and magic in fairy tales than fairies. However, just because there is a talking animal in a story does not mean that the story is a fairy tale.

Steven Swann Jones said that fairy tales were different from other sorts of folktales because of magic. Davidson and Chaudri say that "transformation (changing)" is the most important part of a fairy tale.

Some like to use the German expression *Märchen* or "wonder tale"^[13] instead of fairy tale. For example, in his 1977 edition of *The Folktale*, Thompson said that fairy tales were "a tale of some length involving a succession of motifs or episodes. It moves in an unreal world without definite locality or definite creatures and is filled with the marvelous. In this never-never land, humble heroes kill adversaries (enemies), succeed to kingdoms and marry princesses." The characters and motifs of fairy tales are simple: princesses and girls taking care of geese; youngest sons and brave princes; ogres, giants, dragons, and trolls; wicked stepmothers and false heroes; fairy godmothers and other magic helpers, often talking horses, or foxes, or birds; rules, and people breaking rules.

A fairy tale, fairytale, wonder tale, magic tale, or *Märchen* is an instance of a folklore genre that takes the form of a short story. Such stories typically feature entities such as dwarfs, dragons, elves, fairies, giants, gnomes, goblins, griffins, mermaids, talking animals, trolls, unicorns, or witches, and usually magic or enchantments. In most cultures, there is no clear line separating myth from folk or fairy tale; all these together form the literature of preliterate societies. Fairy tales may be distinguished from other folk narratives such as legends (which generally involve belief in the veracity of the events described) and explicit moral tales, including beast fables. In less technical contexts, the term is also used to describe something blessed with unusual happiness, as in "fairy-tale ending" (a happy ending) or "fairy-tale romance". Colloquially, the term "fairy tale"

or "fairy story" can also mean any far-fetched story or tall tale; it is used especially of any story that not only is not true, but could not possibly be true. Legends are perceived as real; fairy tales may merge into legends, where the narrative is perceived both by teller and hearers as being grounded in historical truth. However, unlike legends and epics, fairy tales usually do not contain more than superficial references to religion and to actual places, people, and events; they take place "once upon a time" rather than in actual times. Fairy tales occur both in oral and in literary form; the name "fairy tale" ("conte de fées" in French) was first ascribed to them by Madame d'Aulnoy in the late 17th century. Many of today's fairy tales have evolved from centuries-old stories that have appeared, with variations, in multiple cultures around the world. The history of the fairy tale is particularly difficult to trace because only the literary forms can survive. Still, according to researchers at universities in Durham and Lisbon, such stories may date back thousands of years, some to the Bronze Age more than 6,500 years ago. Fairy tales, and works derived from fairy tales, are still written today. Folklorists have classified fairy tales in various ways. The Aarne-Thompson classification system and the morphological analysis of Vladimir Propp are among the most notable. Other folklorists have interpreted the tales' significance, but no school has been definitively established for the meaning of the tales.

Types of Fairy Tales

There are no rules that define fairy tales. Therefore, they are categorized by their elements, types, or motifs.

Here are some of those types and examples of stories that fit those types:

- Supernatural Adversaries: *Hansel and Gretel (Ganzel va Gretel)*, *Red Riding Hood (Qizil shapkacha)*
- Supernatural or Enchanted Relatives: *Sleeping Beauty (Uyqudagi malika)*, *Beauty and the Beast (Sohibjamol va maxluq)*
- Supernatural Helpers: *Cinderella (Zolushka)*, *Puss In Boots (Etik kiygan mushuk)*
- Magic Objects: *The Magic Ring (Sehrli uzuk)*, *Aladdin (Alovuddin)*
- Supernatural Power or Knowledge: *The White Snake*, *Ali Baba*
- Religious Tales: *The Three Green Twigs*, *The Flower of Lily-Lo*
- Realistic Tales: *The Falsely Accused Wife*, *Ariadne*
- Tales of Fate: *The Robber Bridegroom*, *Oedipus (Aarne-Thompson)*

The Importance of using Fairy Tales

Fairy tales are crucial because they spark the imagination. They give us an outlet for experiencing things in our minds before we experience them in the real world. It is where the troubles of the real world can meet the supernatural and mix things up. In a fairy tale anything can happen and any kind of creature can exist, and when anything can happen, we can find solutions to things in our real lives. Through imagination, we learn about our world. We can explore outcomes and possibilities.

In folk tales, wonderful heroes who protect the country like the apple of an eye are glorified, women's rights are protected, long distances are brought closer, bad habits and undesirable vices in people's characters are criticized, bravery, dexterity, bravery, the ideas of hard work, honesty, loyalty, and generosity are glorified. Storytellers were called "storytellers" and "matalchi" in ancient times. A characteristic feature of fairy tales is that fantasy is given a lot of space in them, figurative tools such as exaggeration and hyperbole are used. If you notice, in fairy tales, the positive hero definitely wins over evil, injustice, oppression, and celebrates good. Because the heroes of fairy tales represent the hopes and interests of the people. From time immemorial, fairy tales have educated the people, especially the young generation, in the spirit of humanitarianism, love for the country, truthfulness and honesty, hard work, politeness and humility. Tales can be on different topics. They are conventionally divided into animal tales, magical tales, life-household tales, comic tales.

Animal tales are fantastic stories that everyone is interested in. The main content in them is figurative, that is, it has a figurative meaning. For example, cunning and hypocrisy through a fox, bloodthirstiness, a wolf is expressed. Tales such as "The Wolf and the Fox", "The Revenge of the Goat", "The Greedy Wolf", "Ayikpolvan" are such works. Fairy tales are also fantastic stories that you love and enjoy reading. In them, events are based on magic, fantastic fictions, and the heroes of the work are miraculous people who can do anything. Cursing ignorance, hypocrisy, promoting true human qualities such as intelligence, entrepreneurship, courage, compassion, harmony. Among the imaginary stories created by our people, there is a series of fairy tales that we call life-household tales. Most of the events in such tales are close to life, taken from life.

"Zumrad and Kimmat",

"Bakhtiyar with the Moon",

"Ziyad Batir",

"Tahir and Zuhra",

"Ozodachehra",

"Farhad and Shirin",

"Malikayai Husnabad",

"Uch Aga-ini Batirlar" are such fairy tales. is from The life-household tales that we mentioned above are works that have a certain educational direction, which arouse serious opinions in a person. When you get to know them, you will have a clear idea of bravery, devotion to the country, humanity, loyalty, diligence and generosity, and you will want to have the good qualities of the heroes of fairy tales. We said we will listen to and read fairy tales. The stories we listen to are told in an interesting way by professional storytellers, that is, storytellers. Storytellers don't just tell stories. It would not be wrong to say that every storyteller recreates one or another tale. Because each of them differs according to its style of storytelling, taste, worldview. Also, the storyteller can change the story according to the level and demand of the listeners. In the history of Uzbek folklore, the rise of the fairy tale to the level of a work of art and its preservation to this day, the daughter of Hamrabibi Umarali, the son of Hasan Khudoyberdi, the son of Haydar Baychi, the son of Nurali Nurmat, Husanboy Storytellers like Rasul's son, our matalchi have done great service. The priceless examples of Uzbek folk tales recorded from their mouths still give us spiritual pleasure. In Uzbek literature, poetic and prose works created on the basis of folk tales are also reflected in theater and cinema. Children love to watch plays, films and cartoons based on the plot of interesting tales. Children, according to the creation of fairy tales, there is another type - written fairy tales, which make up a large part of foreign literature, in particular, written Uzbek literature. In the next two or three hundred years, the French storyteller Charles Perrault (1628-1703), the German storytellers Emst Theodor Amadeus Hoffmann (1776-1822), the brothers Jacob Grimm (1785-1863) and WilhelmKarl Grimm (1786-1859), Wilhelm Hauff (1802-1877), the Danish Hans Christian Andersen (1805-1875), the English Oscar Wilde (1854-1900), the Russian storytellers A.

S. Pushkin (1799-1837) devoted exactly ten years of their work to creating wise stories and fairy tales for children. L. N. Tolstoy (1828-1910), K. D. Ushinsky (1824-1870), who worked, made a great contribution to the development of written fairy tales. Uzbek written fairy tales also have a long history. Our great-grandfathers Mahmudhoja Bchbudi, Munavvarqori Abdurashidkhanov, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulla Avloni, Hamza Hakimzada Niyoz, Siddiqi-Ajzi created many instructive tales for the school textbooks they compiled. In the middle of the last century, Hamid Olimjon's "Oygul bilan Bakhtiyor", "Semurg", Sultan Jora's "Zangori Gilam", Shukur Sa'dulla's "Cunning Sparrow", "N'khat Polvan", "Lakma it" fairy tales, "Yoriltash", "The Girl Who Created the Legend", fairy tales and plays "Kachal Polvan" became popular. Later, the

traditions of our writers in the field of storytelling were developed by *H. Tokhtaboyev, A. Obidjon, T. Adashboyev, O'*. Our fairy tale writers like Imonberdiyev continued.

Later works

Illustration of the Russian fairy tale about Vasilisa the Beautiful, showing a rider on a horse in a forest

Ivan Bilibin (1876-1942)'s illustration of the Russian fairy tale about Vasilisa the Beautiful
The Violet Fairy Book (1906)

The first collectors to attempt to preserve not only the plot and characters of the tale, but also the style in which they were told, was the Brothers Grimm, collecting German fairy tales; ironically, this meant although their first edition (1812 & 1815)[41] remains a treasure for folklorists, they rewrote the tales in later editions to make them more acceptable, which ensured their sales and the later popularity of their work.[55]

Such literary forms did not merely draw from the folktale, but also influenced folktales in turn. The Brothers Grimm rejected several tales for their collection, though told orally to them by Germans, because the tales derived from Perrault, and they concluded they were thereby French and not German tales; an oral version of Bluebeard was thus rejected, and the tale of Little Briar Rose, clearly related to Perrault's The Sleeping Beauty, was included only because Jacob Grimm convinced his brother that the figure of Brynhildr, from much earlier Norse mythology, proved that the sleeping princess was authentically Germanic folklore.[56]

This consideration of whether to keep Sleeping Beauty reflected a belief common among folklorists of the 19th century: that the folk tradition preserved fairy tales in forms from pre-history except when "contaminated" by such literary forms, leading people to tell inauthentic tales.[57] The rural, illiterate, and uneducated peasants, if suitably isolated, were the folk and would tell pure folk tales.[58] Sometimes they regarded fairy tales as a form of fossil, the remnants of a once-perfect tale.[59] However, further research has concluded that fairy tales never had a fixed form, and regardless of literary influence, the tellers constantly altered them for their own purposes.[60]

The work of the Brothers Grimm influenced other collectors, both inspiring them to collect tales and leading them to similarly believe, in a spirit of romantic nationalism, that the fairy tales of a country were particularly representative of it, to the neglect of cross-cultural influence. Among those influenced were the Russian Alexander Afanasyev (first published in 1866),[41] the Norwegians Peter Christen Asbjørnsen and Jørgen Moe (first published in 1845),[41] the Romanian Petre Ispirescu (first published in 1874), the English Joseph Jacobs (first published in 1890),[41] and Jeremiah Curtin, an American who collected Irish tales (first published in

1890).[35] Ethnographers collected fairy tales throughout the world, finding similar tales in Africa, the Americas, and Australia; Andrew Lang was able to draw on not only the written tales of Europe and Asia, but those collected by ethnographers, to fill his "coloured" fairy books series.[61] They also encouraged other collectors of fairy tales, as when Yei Theodora Ozaki created a collection, Japanese Fairy Tales (1908), after encouragement from Lang.[62] Simultaneously, writers such as Hans Christian Andersen and George MacDonald continued the tradition of literary fairy tales. Andersen's work sometimes drew on old folktales, but more often deployed fairytale motifs and plots in new tales.[63] MacDonald incorporated fairytale motifs both in new literary fairy tales, such as *The Light Princess*, and in works of the genre that would become fantasy, as in *The Princess and the Goblin* or *Lilith*.

In short, fairy tales are the most effective means of influencing children, and on the basis of fairy tales, children develop human qualities such as humanity, bravery, honesty, truthfulness. Fairy tales develop children's thinking and imagination, logical thinking and It is very important for the formation of the speech and the richness of the speech. Therefore, it is necessary to explain to the parents how to read more books to their children.

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